

Munir's Quintuple-Layered Iceberg Model of Research Scholars

During the pursuit of higher education, we encounter individuals who seek power, harbor exaggerated beliefs about their competence, and aim for control over others. We must put an end to this pattern!

Research and knowledge-based competence are considered key indicators of success for research scholars. However, a significant number of scholars are susceptible to developing superiority of power and intellectual vanity. They firmly believe that their existing knowledge and skills are sufficient for socio-economic survival, failing to recognize the importance of continuous learning. They perceive themselves as immune to academic challenges and limitations. In short, they are resistant to examining personal biases.

Some scholars, whether they enter academia with or without taking breaks, often face challenges with critical writing skills and research literacy. This is perfectly acceptable as long as they remain receptive to learning and intellectual growth. However, in many instances, their positions, experiences, and previous academic titles serve as a shield for them. Their motivation for pursuing further education may primarily be material gain, resulting in a lack of dedication and attentiveness. In addition, they may exhibit arrogance, overconfidence, and deceitful behavior in attempts to dominate others.

This model carries a five-layer process:

1. They seek attention and tend to form superficial connections with others. Maintaining a reputation is paramount to them. They excel in strategic planning and prioritize fabricated success, prestige, and material gain over genuine achievements. Their focus heavily lies on grades. They are self-obsessed and may misuse their position. They may also try to develop close alliances with other mentors, based on fabricated networking.
2. When initial efforts fail to gain confidence, they resort to deception and manipulation. Over time, they fear losing confidence and might portray themselves as victims. They pretend to be vulnerable to garner sympathy while concealing their weaknesses. They may start encountering conflicts between their personal and professional lives, leading some scholars to feel overwhelmed and drop out of education to avoid further embarrassment.
3. In the third phase, scholars often encounter anxiety due to rigorous evaluations and exposure of their weaknesses. While mentors provide guidance, they do not compromise on quality. Clear marking criteria and maintaining professional distance become crucial in overcoming these challenges. Consequently, conflicts, frustration, and gossip may arise among scholars as they navigate through this phase.
4. In the final two phases, the challenges continue and may escalate, leading some scholars to abandon their education out of arrogance and impatience. However, those who persist become resilient. They prioritize ethical academic practices and embrace a lifelong learning mindset. They are aware that their work is not perfect, but remain eager to embrace vulnerability and

seek further refinement. Unfortunately, promoting ethical practices can be challenging due to the prevalence of dishonesty in academic environments.

For teachers: "Strive to maintain honesty, even if the world labels you dishonest. Stay loyal to your profession, and your dignity may be undermined. Educate to prepare competent scholars, knowing that the world will be quick to question your professionalism. The key to maintaining your dignity and integrity despite setbacks lies in your unwavering commitment to your profession. It allows you to negotiate genuinely or choose to leave a toxic academic environment."

It is important to embrace self-acceptance and emphasize the practical application of research skills and knowledge-based competencies among research scholars. Simultaneously, it's important to caution them against the pitfalls of seeking power and nurturing delusions.